

Capacitive Left Hand Finger and Bow Sensors for Synchronization and Rhythmical Regularity Analysis in String Ensembles

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ABSTRACT

In this paper bow and fingerboard sensors for measurements of synchronization between musicians in group music making are introduced. They are evaluated in several performing situations from advanced musicians in a new founded string trio up to a professional, long time experienced string quartet. The small form factor of the sensors allowed to measure synchronization in musicians' daily life situations. These are a rehearsal, tuition in chamber music class, and a concert situation. Additionally, the musicians filled out a questionnaire rating their grade of preparation, the influence of the sensor while playing, and some more data in each recording session. With the sensors, different rhythmic inaccuracies in seemingly simultaneous bow and note changes between the musicians while making music together are measured and quantified. Further a possibility for sensor based rhythmical regularity measurement while playing equal notes is presented. The results of the questionnaire confirm the unobtrusiveness of the setup and the possible use of it in daily performing situations and even on stage. At the end of this paper an outlook for synchronization skills is introduced and possible impacts into the field of new music is shown.

1. INTRODUCTION

A sensor setup for data acquisition and measurements of musical instrument playing parameters, here synchronization in group music making, which is often discussed among musicians, but difficult to objectify. These are synchronization related parameters like rhythmic inaccuracies (delay and anticipation times) in simultaneous finger changes, cues and bow changes and rhythmical regularity of isochronous notes. Several technologies for motion and gestures' detection during instrumental musical playing exist. Diverse works e.g. by Maestre in [1] show several approaches to objectively capture gestures, particularly those associated to the bowing of string instruments. The most used measuring methods are based on the use of acceleration sensors and gyroscopes. Among others, the first sensors applied to violin, bow, and violin gestures were the acceleration sensor on the bow by

Bevilaqua et al. [2]. Wearable, left hand pressure, and position sensors were introduced by Grosshauser et al. in [3]. First measurements of fingers and hand coordination and synchronization between two violinists are carried out in Grosshauser et al. in [4] and of tongue and finger coordination in saxophone playing (Goebel et al. in [5]). Compared to the latter, in this paper a more flexible and partly wireless setup for group measurements is evaluated. To round up the field of musical instrument sensing, hyperinstruments with similar technologies (see Machover in [6]) and the commercially available K Bow by McMillen have to be mentioned. Nevertheless, sensing of synchronization of two or more musicians playing music together is clearly underrepresented in the literature, especially with unobtrusive sensors, allowing unhindered playing and ready for real-life, on stage measurements.

The sensors presented here are small 9 degree-of-freedom (DOF) sensor boards with onboard batteries and SD-card slots, described in sec. 2.2 and shown in Fig. 1 and flexible capacitive left hand finger position sensors (sec. 2.1).

Figure 1. The 9DOF ETHOS module, with the dimensions of 14x45x4 mm and a weight of 4.2 gr. without battery.

They are fixed on the bows and fingerboards and used for measuring rhythmic inaccuracies in synchronized cueing and performing situations of string ensembles. The setup allows precise measurements of the synchronization of two and more musicians while playing together. The

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setup was evaluated with advanced musicians in a recently launched music group and a professional, long time experienced group. The test subjects range from amateur violinists up to professional musicians. We measured different performing situations, ranging from rehearsal, tuition in chamber music class, and a concert situation. We show that the present setup allows unhindered playing while measuring. It further works with a high temporal resolution and can be used in the field of string players, from beginners up to professionals alike. To support musicians and music teachers in daily exercising, particularly during their technical training, here, the sensors allow to show synchronization inaccuracies and regularity parameters, difficult to detect and quantify, but meaningful for music making. The results achieved in the measurements could lead to teaching and practicing support in string instruments. Also the integration of the final set-up into electronic music scenarios and new playing techniques is possible.

2. SENSOR SETUP

For the right hand bowing the 9 DOF ETHOS sensors are used and for the continuous left hand finger position measurement flexible capacitive sensor stripes.

2.1 Flexible Capacitive Finger Position Sensor Stripes

The left hand finger sensors are thin stripes fixed on the fingerboard between the strings of each participant's instrument of the higher strings (Cello not yet). For the capacitive sensor the MPR121 chip from Freescale Semiconductor is used (2 each stripe) and the working principle is shown in Fig. 2. An Arduino Mini connected via I2C is used for data collection and for data transmission to a laptop computer via USB. This solution showed lower and more stable latency than the cap sense library for Arduino (around 25 ms, 40 Hz).

Figure 2. Working principle of the capacitive sensor stripes. Each red area (Area 1, Area 2, ... Area n copper areas) on the top layer is read out independently. This allows continuous finger position detection of each finger with a median sampling frequency of 50 Hz.

The resolution of the final setup is, but not limited to, around 2 mm depending on the placement of the fingers more between or on the strings, but enough for position and note detection, the scanning frequency is around 100 Hz. If a finger is put on the fingerboard, one or two of the stripes

are touched. With this information the actually played string is detected.

Figure 3. Capacitive sensor stripes are fixed on the fingerboard for continuous finger position capturing.

2.2 ETHOS 9DOF Sensors

The used ETHOS sensor (see Harms et al. in [7]) is a 9DOF miniature board with 3 axes acceleration, 3 axes gyroscopes, and 3 axes magnetometer. A three-axis accelerometer (Linear Technology, LIS3LV02DL) is implemented and can be configured to resolve $2/6 G$ with a 16-bit resolution. Earth magnetic field is sensed by an integrated digital compass IC (Honeywell, HMC5843) in all three axes. A three-axes gyroscope (Invensense, ITG-3200) allows sensing of the rate of change with a maximum measurement range of 2000 degr./s at resolution of 16-bit. We use a sampling frequency of 500 Hz , meaning temporal resolution of 2 ms . It is powered with a 140 mAh LiPo battery for at least 3 hours recording time at this sampling frequency. The ETHOS unit dimensions are $W \times L \times H$ of $14 \times 45 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$. The central processing unit of ETHOS is a 16-bit dsPIC. The ETHOS sensors are fixed on the bow of each musicians for motion capturing (see Fig. 4).

It features an integrated real time clock, which is crucial for tagging of data and synchronization of multiple ETHOS units. The system gathers the individual information by three MEMS devices: an accelerometer, a gyroscope and a magnetic field sensor. Moreover a temperature sensor and system power monitor are implemented for automatic self-calibration. The maximum difference of the clocks are 40 msec each 3600 sec . In our study we only used the data of 600 sec , meaning a deviation based on the run time difference of the real time clocks of max-

Figure 4. The ETHOS sensors fixed on the bow.

imum 6.67 msec . Grosshauser et al. in [4] demonstrated, that there is no delay between the bowing initial acceleration and the sound generation at the musical instrument. Based on this measurement we estimated, that our setup is precise enough for synchronization measurements. For the synchronization measurement, only the bow acceleration data are analyzed.

Each board further comprises an 8-channel ultra low power ANT module for wireless communication. ANT allows interconnection of multiple ETHOS units for creation of wireless body area networks (BAN). This network could be extended by other ANT or ANT+ enabled devices, e.g. a heart rate belt, step counter, or GPS module. Moreover, it allows to interface the unit with mobile computers. While the ANT standard is impractical for streaming of raw data, the bandwidth would allow a transmission of gathered orientation data at a maximum frequency of up to 200 Hz . For the study introduced in this paper, the sampling rate was too low. Due to this fact, ANT was not used, therefore the data were recorded on a SD card. The onboard microSD card slot was used (see Fig. 1) to store data, timestamps and system configuration. MicroSD flash memory is of small dimensions, available with high capacities and can be easily replaced in case of low memory. System power is provided by an external lithium-polymer battery with a nominal voltage of 3.7 V . If the system is connected to an USB port the system battery is loaded by an integrated Li-Ion battery charger. In our standard configuration we use a miniature 300 mAh battery with $W \times L \times H$ dimensions of $20 \times 30 \times 3\text{ mm}^3$. In the test setup of this experiment, we used a smaller battery with 140 mAh to reduce the weight in the bows.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the bow acceleration data synchronized with the video recording. The data show additionally to the video the acceleration peaks of the bow changes of each player. This example shows an accurate bow change with no delays of all four musicians.

3. MEASUREMENTS AND RESULTS

A string trio and a string quartet was measured in different playing situations for one hour each. The string trio is a new founded group with advanced and professional musicians. The string quartet is an experienced group with four professional musicians. The music pieces were all of classicism from Haydn and Beethoven. The situations were daily rehearsals, tuition in a chamber music class, and a concert situation. The different situations should proof that unhindered playing with the presented setup is possible. This was evaluated with a questionnaire, results see in sec. 3.1. The sampling frequency of the capacitive left hand finger sensor will be increased due to low temporal resolution of around 10 ms . Each recording session was recorded with an A/V camera. The recorded data were analyzed per hand with a labeling tool, see Fig. 5. The acceleration peaks of the bow changes are easy recognizable in the data viewer. You simply mark the clear bow change points and if two, the time between these two points is calculated. The additional A/V view simplifies this task and helps to find the key points.

3.1 Results of the Questionnaire

To obtain information about the unobtrusiveness of the setup, a questionnaire was filled out before and after each recording session by the musicians of each test group. First a self estimation about their own mood and tiredness was ask to avoid e.g. negative influence of these factors to the reaction times. No noticeable extreme conditions were indicated, other than an increase of excitement before the concert. The participants were between 31 and 44 years old. The over all average age was 34.71 years (Trio: 38, Quartet: 32.25), the average experience of musical instrument playing was 24.85 years (Trio: 24.33 and Quartet: 25.25). There was one advanced musician and 6 professionals. All participants state no or positive influence of the measurement setup and the usefulness of the data. For further information please see Fig. 6. The sensors were not distracting, but still were noticed by 4 of 7 musicians. The new founded trio stated positive influence of the setup while playing with it. According to the trio members, this is due to the fact, that they concentrated more on synchronized playing, knowing that it is measured. All participants agreed, that the measured data are useful, 2 two of them rated the data as “very useful”. An interesting aspect is, that even the professional quartet did not feel hindered while playing and suggested a data recording in a real concert situation.

3.2 Measurement of Temporal Inaccuracies in Synchronized Music Making

The stacked sensors are synchronized with clear acceleration movements in front of the camera, allowing a later re-synchronization of sensor and video data with the data labeling tool (see Fig. 5). The synchronization is done before and after the recording.

The measurement of the string quartet showed significantly lower delay times while playing together in com-

	Age	Instrument	Status	The sensor setup was/had		Value of the data, useful, useless?
				distracting?	influence?	
Average Quartet	32.25					
Violin1	33	Violin	Professional	noticed but nondistracting	no infl	very useful
Cello	33	Cello	Professional	nondistracting	no infl	useful
Violin2	31	Violin	Professional	noticed but nondistracting	no infl	very useful
Viola	32	Viola	Professional	nondistracting	no infl	useful
TrioCello	34	Cello	Advanced	noticed but nondistracting	pos influence	useful
TrioViolin	36	Violin	Professional	nondistracting	pos influence	useful
TrioViola	44	Viola	Professional	noticed but nondistracting	pos influence	useful
Average Trio	38					
Average Overall	34.71					

Figure 6. Statistical data of the test subjects. Each participant filled out a questionnaire after each measurement.

Figure 7. Delay between the earliest and latest musician in synchronized cueing.

parison to the trio. The average delay between the musicians of the string quartet was 19 ms, maximum is 98 ms, minimum 0 ms. The average delay of the trio is 43 ms, maximum is 171 ms, minimum is 0.05 ms. Also the delay in cueing situations is higher in the trio compared to the quartet (see Fig. 7). The left hand sensor data are collected via USB and recorded with a laptop computer without delay. The temporal resolution of around 20 ms was not good enough to find reliable left hand synchronization data. Only the bow changes are considered in the analysis.

In Fig. 8 the temporal deviations of bow changes are shown. In a straight series of eighth notes, faint delays are recognizable. This could be due to expression reasons, but e.g. in rhythm training situations, this temporal analysis is crucial. The sampling frequency of the capacitive sensor stripes is too slow to get precise synchronization information, especially of the experienced quartet. Delay higher than 20 ms can be detected. Also coordination measurements between left hand fingers and right hand bowing of each musician are possible, again with the above mentioned temporal limitation.

Figure 8. Rhythmical regularity: Delays of bow and note changes of isochronous, equally long notes.

4. POSSIBILITIES FOR NEW MUSIC INTERFACES IN PERFORMANCE AND TEACHING

If the musicians control synchronization delays, this playing method could be used for musical expression. Live data transmission with the integrated ANT rf transmitter Bluetooth allows beside the visualization of the acceleration, magnetometer, and gyroscope data the mapping of these data with musical effects or sound generation. Augmenting the sensor data with additional feedback e.g. sonification could be useful for synchronization training. Furthermore the sonification itself could be used as an expression parameter e.g. like micro-rhythmical patterns. The simplicity of the setup further allows easy integration of the measurement method in the course of daily practicing and rehearsing. Without wireless data transmission, every sensor can be fixed on the bows after calibration and after rehearsing, the data can be visualized and observed in standard chart programs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The setup presented in this paper is a further step into getting more objective data in music making and performing. Beside the unobtrusiveness of the setup (based on the statements given in written form on the questionnaire filled

from the participants in every measurement session and on interviews and discussions), findings of latencies between musicians while playing together are shown. Although synchronization is just one parameter of many, it is a very significant one. Measurements in different playing situations and different levels will allow comparisons, not only between two or more groups, but also for progress tracking in learning and exercising situations. In this direction, also the effectiveness of exercises can be observed. The individual observation of rhythmical regularity provides useful information in daily exercising.

In the future observations, tests for the importance and the stability of the measurement will be made. When combining measurements with the right exercises, the latency factor could help beginners or new-formed music groups to improve their playing skills. To do so, the resolution of the left hand sensors will be increased.

Furthermore, the work represents a new step towards novel measurement setups to quantify usually hidden parameters pivotal to music making, which are difficult to be objectively shown. While usually the individual impression of “uncoordinated” or “not in time” playing may be right, its objective depiction and quantifying is a challenge. By using the presented measurement setup and sensors it is possible to measure parameters like rhythmic inaccuracies and irregularities.

The next steps will also include the simplification of the present setup and its refinement to still enhance its already high acceptability among musicians and especially the increase of the sampling frequency, spatial resolution and the size of the capacitive left hand finger sensor. Easily understandable real-time feedback modalities and the use of the sensor setup in other types of musical instruments will be a long-term goal. This may ultimately contribute to the development of new methods of instrumental training and provide new interfaces based on traditional instrument for musical expression.

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